

IDEA: Integrating Diversity in Evaluation and Assessment of Researchers – Experiences from Amsterdam

Workshop 2
Mapping diversity along career trajectory

Introduction

- Short round of introduction
 - Name
 - Role
 - What you found striking about the infographic
 - Any questions

IDEA Project Aim

Develop an **action plan** on how to **integrate researcher diversity** in the researcher assessment reforms taking place in **the R&R program** at the VU, using generative design co-creation methodology consisting of **4 workshops**.

Q1
Jan-
March

Map of intersection –
diversity issues and
researcher assessment

Q3
Jul-Sep

Final draft of action plan

Workshop 1

Workshop 2

Workshop 3

Workshop 4

Inventory of strategies

Q2
Apr-Jun

First draft of action plan

Q4
Oct-Dec

FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO THE LEAKY PIPELINE PHENOMENON

	Factors	Suggestion solutions
1	Lack of clear and transparent promotion criteria	Transparent, unambiguous and well-communicated promotion criteria
2	Disproportionally high workloads of invisible service work	Equal distribution of labor
3	Sexism and racial discrimination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acknowledge identity in knowledge production over 'objectivity' • Promote inclusivity, diversity, and equity through policies and trainings, and monitor • Role models
4	Exclusion from professional and support networks	Culturally competent mentorship
5	Precarious working conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for parents and caretakers • Do not expect uniform productivity
6	Lack of (financial) support for engaging in true research interests.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide growth possibilities • Reward and value research on diversity, equity and inclusion

QUESTIONS TO EXPLORE

2

- How attractive is VU as an employer for different demographic and professional groups?
- Will the proposed changes meaningfully impact the balance between valuing teaching and research?
- To what extent do ambiguous promotion criteria pose a barrier to achieving diversity?
- How do current criteria limit mobility and interdisciplinarity within VU?
- Why is there no specific targeting of PhD candidates or Team Science initiatives, and what are the implications?

Analysis faculty plans

MAPPING DIVERSITY WITHIN FACULTY POLICIES

This workshop

Goal: create **map** of career trajectory and where on it opportunities and threats for diversity lie

In terms of privacy

- We will use anonymized data from the workshops – nothing linking to personal information
- Please do not put information on boards/slides which are personal
- We are not taking notes - please put all input on slides

Some ground rules

- *You are in charge of content, we guide the process*
- *Listen to each other (no talking over) and be cordial*
- *Both experiential and content expertise is welcome and appreciated*
- *Goal is not necessarily to agree, but to lead to deeper understanding*
- *Any others from your side?*

Exercise 1: Career trajectories

Individually, reflect on and visualize your own career trajectory or that of someone you know who meets IDEA's target group (15 minutes).

1. Pick one of the formats here or draw your own
2. Add important considerations

[Anonymized institution]

We see a general trend for researchers that their trajectory looks as follows:

- PhD in NL/abroad
- Postdoc abroad
- Senior postdoc in NL
- Assistant Prof in NL

[researchers have children frequently in the postdoc phase]

[if researchers have children during PhD, they usually don't go abroad]

Also: physician researchers usually obtain their PhD and then pursue their clinical training/specialization, followed by postdoctoral research. Both happen in the same place, making international mobility impossible.

A lack of international mobility negatively impacts researcher evaluation, as it is seen as a lack of developing independence.

Person 2 someone I Know

UD2 -> 10 years focus on education

PhD promotion

UD1 -> 3 years ago after PhD defense

//<> no clear criteria for Associated Prof step
ambition is focus on education

Person 3: from my team

[Anonymized to research support staff]

- PhD student in [anonymized]
- First career step at our HEI: [anonymized]
- Current career step: [anonymized to research support staff] excellent performance
- Career perspectives look very promising, the person is extremely talented and growing all the time
- Next step could be senior researcher

Person 4

- Undergraduate and Masters degrees (scholarship)
- PhD abroad (scholarship)
- Moved back home for family reasons and found work as full-time lecturer (no research time)
- Baby 1 (maternity leave)
- Moved to different city for family reasons
- Part-time work as [anonymized to researchers]-then full-time
- Baby 2 (maternity leave)
- Applied for postdoctoral scholarship (no longer eligible for some; not funded)
- Full time work as [anonymized to researcher]
- Left research career

Person 5

Neurodivergence & academia = a love-hate relationship with many ups and downs

Threats

Supervision depends on understanding individuals, not too embedded in overall system

Rigid work environment

Deadlines, temporary contracts, no guarantee for future career after PhD, risk of saying yes to too many things, burnout

Always working in an environment where you are an outlier

Invisibility and misunderstanding of what neurodivergence is

Support exists for students, but not sure whether it exists for your career development

Opportunities

Lack of research on adult women key reason to pursue academic career (now PhD) to begin with

Great pattern recognition skills, creative thinking

I only think of it as a disability in *certain* environments

Right supervision helps to put it to your / research' advantage!

Diverse interests might lead to diverse opportunities in academia

Small things like a silent room can already be helpful

Person 6

- Unfunded master's, working fulltime while pursuing master's at night

- Threat: financial hurdle

- (Partially) unfunded PhD

- Threat: financial hurdle/time restraints while pursuing paid work on side of PhD

- Previously on precarious temp contract + visa sponsorship in role that is in academia, but not as academic

- Threat: instability, especially in current political climate, less ability to focus on research in current role

Professor/[Other role related to diversity deleted for anonymization]

Threat: As I was not awarded a doctoral scholarship and had to relocate to another region, I undertook paid teaching assignments in order to support myself financially during the PhD.

PhD in [anonymized] (2006)

Recruited as permanent researcher at another University

Threat: After more than ten years of academic work in a specific disciplinary field (Gender Studies), I was required to change sector/field due to institutional recruitment policies adopted by my university (Sociology of Territory, that was considered more useful and “appealing” for the University.. This shift forced me to partially restart my academic career, as only part of my previous publications and research activities could be recognized in the new field.

[position anonymized_

Threat: Difficult balance between investment in my own scientific career and the mandatory administrative and institutional commitments (lot of academic care work), and my family and private life

Person 8

Person 9

- [anonymized] years of undergraduate studies
- [anonymized] years as a research fellow
- [anonymized] years of specialized research [location anonymized]
- [Details anonymized → x years as researcher in different positions]

Now become an associate professor

Person 10

Mixed marginal & privileged background

- Strong standard early academic career
- Break for family
- Continued seemingly strong (mid career)
- Hard stop
- 3 new attempts
- Undercover researcher, ambiguous

Possible new development: exploring roles in coaching, to scale DEI impact, from project-level implementation to more concrete and systemic influence.

Transition to Applied Research & DEI Strategy

[anonymized number of years]: Organizational development, gender equality, [anonymized] projects.

DEI Challenge: Translating Policy into Practice, and in particular, facing resistance to change in a STEM-heavy, male-dominated context met with cultural pushback.

Early Academic Career [anonymized number, 5+]

years : a Ph.D. and postdoc in
[anonymized]

DEI Challenge: Structural Precarity

[Anonymized institution]
pHD/post doc → assistant
professor (UD)-->
associate professor→ full
professor

Less and less spots, less
and less women filling the
spots→ less experience
(papers hours of research
etc.) because of pregnancy
leave and no
compensation for
pregnancy leave

Person 13

PhD trajectory

[Anonymized to different institutions]

Finalized in [anonymized] years

Working at a [anonymized] organization [anonymized] years [role anonymized]

Working at [anonymized to: different type of higher education institution] for [anonymized] years

University Full Prof

Person 14

Person 15

Exercise 1: Career trajectories

In breakout rooms (30 minutes):

1. Share your individual reflections
2. Select one template/format/career trajectory map to continue working with in the next exercise (and place on slides 28-30)

Breakout room 1: Shared template/format/map

Breakout room 2: Shared template/format/map

Duality of being in and out of academia

Challenges traditional leaky pipeline metaphor

Sometimes choices, sometimes having to zigzag

Horizontal growth

Academic work vs work in the academia → focusing on academics narrowly reinforces linear trajectory

Breakout room 3: Shared template/format/map

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Also: physician researchers usually obtain their PhD and then pursue their clinical training/specialization, followed by postdoctoral research. Both happen in the same place, making international mobility impossible.

A lack of international mobility negatively impacts researcher evaluation, as it is seen as a lack of developing independence.

Exercise 2: Critical moments for diversity

In breakout rooms (30 minutes):

1. Individually, add ideas about critical moments for diversity in the chosen map/template/format (copy and paste into slide 32-34)
2. Discuss all the ideas

Bad
moments/thre
ats/risks

Good
moments/opp
ortunities

Breakout room 2: Critical moments for diversity

Breakout room 3: Critical moments for diversity

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Closing

- Next steps: processing of input (also with input from workshop on May 22) to finalize a map of critical moments for diversity in researcher evaluations
- Last input from you: what is 1 thing we should keep in mind for the rest of the project?

What to keep in mind for the rest of the project

Comment deleted for anonymization

Universities need to have criteria that align with those of funding organisations. Collaboration is key

Don't forget neurodivergent people

Mobility is a key point for achieving inclusion

Academic freedom is only possible if we take responsibility ourselves, rather than asking funders / regulators to force change

Don't forget trans women and trans femme non binary people

More flexibility in career paths should be recognized. For example: now people who cannot get personal grants within a certain time frame have a set back when evaluated for promotions.

Important to collect data on representation, funding, salaries, etc. to document inequalities

Different Career path in Academia-> research; education; board and management. Values should be the same Research professors; educational professors; Dean and so on.

Need to break the myth that excellence and inclusion are in opposition

We should reflect together on how to change the meaning of "Excellence" in academia

Intersectionality is extremely relevant and still largely under-discussed, with even less being done about it in terms of policy.

Let's keep collaborating and organizing! We achieve more when we are together and foster intersectional solidarity

An independent university grants you the right to say 'no' without facing severe and solely personal repercussions